

Properties of Composite Box Beams under Combined Impact Loading

K. Mizukawa, T. Fujii, K. Itami

Faculty of Engineering, Osaka City University, 3-138, Sugimoto 3-chome, Sumiyoshi-ku, Osaka 558, Japan

ABSTRACT

The effect of combined flexural and torsional stresses on the fracture characteristics of thin-walled square and rectangular box beams has been investigated under static and impact loadings by means of newly designed apparatus capable of applying flexural and torsional moments in various proportion. The box structure was fabricated from chopped strand mat and unsaturated polyester resin using a pressure bag method. Failure stresses in the impact and static cases were compared. Comparison between experimentally determined strengths and the theoretical predictions using simple failure criteria were presented.

INTRODUCTION

A major limitation involved in the use of composite materials in structural applications is insufficient stiffness performance as compared with metallic materials. Thus sandwich construction consists of two thin fiber reinforced plastics facings separated by a thick layer of low density core has been used to avoid the problem. In the use of the structure as beam, it may be sometimes subjected to torsional stress combined with flexural moment. The strength of the beam depends on the failure in weak core. In order to improve on this aspect, it is effective to utilize a box structure. This structure has been well known as the box type spar construction of airplane wing. In regard to the composite materials, trial production of striking lever in shuttle is reported, and the possibility of applying to the structural member of ships and vehicles.

The present work is planned and carried out with a view to improving the strength properties of sandwich beam by use of a box structure. First, an adhesively bonded geometry is adopted for production of the box specimens(1); namely previously laminated facings are bonded with epoxy adhesives on both sides of the sandwich specimens contained silica balloon (100-140 μm in diameter) filled unsaturated polyester core. A defect of this structure is the inability to provide the inherent strength of the laminates due to the adherent corners. In order to eliminate the disadvantage, a pressure bag process is adopted to produce the thin-walled box structure which has no adherent portion. Attempts are made to clear the combined and loading rate effect of flexural and torsional moments on the strength of box beams. A testing apparatus capable of applying flexural and torsional moments in any desired proportions is designed and constructed for this purpose.

EXPERIMENTAL

Specimen Fabrication

Square and rectangular thin-walled box structures were fabricated from randomly oriented glass mat (REM-450CM) and unsaturated polyester resin (Polymal 3272) using a pressure bag process. The technique for making the structures was as follows. Polyvinyl chloride tubes of 32 mm outside diameter were used as mandrels. These were covered with a single layer of polyester release film. Three turns of resin impregnated chopped strand mat were wrapped around the mandrel. The mandrel was then removed and a rubber tube was inserted. The material was cured in the square or rectangular sectional mold held at 80°C for 40 min. by pressurizing the rubber bladder on the inside of the wrapping reinforcement. This method produced box structures of 200 mm length, and uniform wall thickness and curvature of corners. Specimen ends of 60 mm were filled with resin mortar to prevent the fracture by chucking. Sectional view of the specimens is shown in Figure 1.

Testing Apparatus

A schematic arrangement of the apparatus is shown in Figure 2 and a general view in Photograph 1. This is so designed as to make possible either simultaneous or simple application of uniform flexural and torsional moments on a centrally located specimen(1). Moments are applied by means of loading arms(2) compressed by indenters(3), the position and the number of the indenters can be adjusted to exert the required magnitude and types of moments. The apparatus is characterized by the use of a set of load supporting unit which comprises ball slides(4), and a pair of pins(5) and ball bearings(6). These units allow the angular rotation about the specimen axis associated with the twisting of the specimen as well as the independent simple motion. For the combined stressed test, indenters are located in a skew symmetrical fashion in relation to the test specimen as shown in Figure 2 with the pins driven out from the housing of the ball slide through the side plate of the supporting unit. If swivelling motion of the specimen is only required, an inclination of the shaft(7) can be prevented by connecting the housing and the side plate of the unit with the pins. In the case of flexural test, indenters are fitted on both side of the loading arms in symmetrical with respect to the specimen axis, and the ball slide is disconnected from the side plate of the unit. One chuck(8) can merely rotate, while the other is free to rotate and move longitudinally, so that as the specimen is stressed no tensile stress is built up in it. The apparatus is capable of applying a twisting moment of up to 250 Nm together with a superposed flexural moment of up to 300 Nm.

Testing Procedure

Static tests were performed by the apparatus mounted on an Instron type testing machine, Simadzu Autograph DSS-5000, with a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min. Impact tests were also conducted by the apparatus in a drop weight machine developed in our laboratory. Strains and moments were measured by strain gages bonded on the specimen and the shaft connected to the freely rotating chuck respectively. The signals from these were amplified and fed to a transient memory, so that a stress-strain characteristic was able to be plotted. The modes of failures of all specimens were identified from visual examination of failed surface.

Prior to testing with the box structures, the tensile, flexural and in-plane shear strength of the laminates consisting of the same component and construction as the thin-walled structure were measured for various stress rates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of the stress rate on the tensile, flexural, and in-plane shear fracture stresses of the laminates consist of the same component as the thin-walled structure is shown in Figure 3 where stresses are normalized with respect to the

static strength. The relationship is represented by straight lines of the same slope regardless of the loading modes. This can be expressed as(2,3):

$$\sigma_c = \sigma_{c0} \left(\frac{\dot{\sigma}_c}{\dot{\sigma}_{c0}} \right)^a \quad (1)$$

,where σ_c : Impact fracture stress
 σ_{c0} : Static fracture stress
 $\dot{\sigma}_c$: Impact stress rate
 $\dot{\sigma}_{c0}$: Static stress rate
 a : Constant

In this case, a is 0.0453.

The static and impact flexural, torsional and combined flexural-torsional specimens were failed in the modes illustrated in Figure 4. The fracture mode was similar to both cases, although considerable fiber/matrix debonding over the whole gage length was observed. In the rectangular box specimens, sometimes observed a concave deformation in torsional and flexural-torsional tests. Photographs 2,3 and 4 show the failed specimens tested in various loading modes. Static and impact flexural-torsional strengths of the square and rectangular box beams are indicated in Figure 5 to Figure 8. In any case failure stresses are consistent with the fracture modes. According to maximum work theory(4,5), the failure criterion is given by:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X}\right)\left(\frac{\sigma_2}{X}\right) + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{X}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (2)$$

,where $\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \tau_{12}$: Normal and shear stress in the direction of the principal material axis
 X, Y, S : Strength in the principal material direction and in-plane shear strength

In order to explain the effect of the combined flexural and torsional stress on the fracture characteristics of the beams, the following experimental equation is proposed on referring to Eq.(2).

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_1}{X}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{Y}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (3)$$

Results for this equation are also drawn by solid lines in Figure 5 to Figure 8. These curves coincide with the experimental results, thus it appears to be reasonable to estimate the strength of composite box beams in combined stress state by Eq.(3).

CONCLUSIONS

A study has been made of the effect of combined flexural and torsional stresses on the fracture characteristics of thin-walled square and rectangular box beams under and impact loadings. Failure stresses in the impact case were higher than the corresponding static values for square type specimens, and were consistent with the fracture modes.

The variation of the fracture behavior and the combined flexural-torsional strength with static and impact loadings has been obtained for thin-walled composite beams. It was found that important relation exists between the fracture mode and strength. It has been also shown that two failure criteria examined could be used successfully to predicted the combined impact flexural-torsional strength of thin-walled composite beam structure.

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t=0.87
R=2.70

Figure 1 Sectional view of test specimens.

Figure 2 Schematic arrangement of testing apparatus.

Photograph 1 General view of testing apparatus mounted in drop weight machine.

Figure 3 Relationship between stress rate and strength ratio for the laminate consists of the same component as the thin-walled structure.

Figure 5 Static flexural-torsional strength of square box structure.

Figure 6 Impact flexural-torsional strength of square box structure.

Figure 7 Static flexural-torsional strength of rectangular box structure

Figure 8 Impact flexural-torsional strength of rectangular box structure.